

The
BRITISH
UNIVERSITY
IN EGYPT

FACULTY OF ARTS AND HUMANITIES

UNIVERSITY OF MINNESOTA
MEDICAL SCHOOL

*International Symposium
on
Medical Humanities*

7th of May 2024

Programme

Everything that Makes Us Human
The Potentials of Medical Humanities

Pre-Symposium Event
Faculty of Arts and Humanities
The British University in Egypt
Undergraduate Students Contributions
May 7th, 2024

Department of English Language and Literature	
10:00 - 11:30 (CLT) (GMT+3) Panel One	Opening Note Assoc. Prof. Walaa Hassan Organising Committee Chair: Mervat Shukry “Examining the Concept of Beauty, Youth and Ethics Through a Freudian Psychoanalytical Reading of The Picture of <i>Dorian Gray</i> by Oscar Wilde” Miral Hossam (The British University in Egypt) “A Lacanian reading of Essam Youssef’s <i>A ¼ Gram</i> ” Youssef El Khashab (The British University in Egypt) The intertwinement of Christian identity and psychological wellness in <i>Jane Eyre</i> ” Nathalie Maher (The British University in Egypt) “Preferred Learning Styles of Egyptian English Language Learners Post Covid-19 Pandemic” Farida Mohamed, Wesam Morsi, and Tasbeeh Yasser (The British University in Egypt)

International Symposium on Medical Humanities
Faculty of Arts and Humanities
The British University in Egypt
May 7th, 2024

Opening Session	
12:30- 13:00 (CLT) (GMT+3)	Prof. Shadia Fahim Dean of the Faculty of Arts and Humanities, The British University in Egypt Assoc. Professor Rania M Rafik Khalil Acting Vice Dean for Research and Postgraduate Studies Faculty of Arts and Humanities, BUE Director - Research Centre for Irish Studies (RCIS) Symposium Convenor

Keynote Address 1	
13:00-13:30 (CLT) (GMT+3)	Dr. Lucy Burke, Manchester Metropolitan University, The UK “Zones of Indistinction or Memory Trouble: Thinking about Dementia, writing and Personhood” Chair: Ahlam Othman
Parallel Panels: One, Two, and Three	
13:30-14:30 (CLT) (GMT+3) Panel One	Multimodality and Medical Humanities Chair: Walaa Hassan <i>“Aphasia as represented in the TV show <i>House M. D.</i>”</i> Marian Morcos (Ain Shams University, Egypt) <i>“Balto: Comedic Representation of Medical Professionals in TV Drama”</i> May Soliman (The British University in Egypt) <i>“Visual persuasion in Selected English & Arabic Covid-19 Editorial Cartoons (2020-2021): Vaccine Portrayal”</i> Basma Talaat El-Sayed (Ain Shams University, Egypt)
13:30-14:30 (CLT) (GMT+3) Panel Two	The Potential for Healing Chair: Lucy Burke <i>“Trapped in a Toxic Tango: Fictional Narcissistic Relationships Unraveled”</i> Ahlam Othman (The British University in Egypt) <i>“Hunger from Fat Studies to Health Humanities: The Potential of the Humanities”</i> Maha Mohamed Hosny (Helwan University, Egypt) <i>“Healing Miracles in the Gospel of Luke: A Literary-Cinematic Paleopathological Reading from the Gospel to the Screen”</i> Amgad Hanna (Ain Shams University, Egypt)
13:30-14:30 (CLT) (GMT+3)	Physical Sickness and its Discontents (1) Chair: Noha Hanafy <i>“Interrogating the intersection between Disability and Gender Discourse in the context of Medical Humanities: A Reading of Mahesh Dattani’s play Tara”</i> Habib Subhan (Diamond Harbour Women's University, India) <i>“Renal Failure: A Janus-Faced Illness Narrative”</i> Hoda El-Hadary (British University in Egypt)

Panel Three	<p>“Disability, Sexuality, and the Medical Apparatus in Indra Sinha’s <i>Animal’s People</i>” Rimjhim Bhattacharjee (Udaynarayanpur Madhabilata Mahavidyalaya, India)</p> <p>“Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) in Zoulfa Katouh’s <i>As Long as the Lemon Trees Grow</i>” Mai Elgeballi (The British University in Egypt)</p>
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Parallel Panels: Four, Five and Six	
14:30-15:30 (CLT) (GMT+3) Panel Four	<p style="text-align: center;">Mental and Physical Disorders in Linguistic Research</p> <p>Chair: May Soliman</p> <p>“Gender and Emotional Expressivity in the Narratives of Social Anxiety Disorder (SAD) Patients: An Appraisal Study of Selected Blogs.” Rawda Ibrahim - Ghada Elsayed - Abeer Aly El-Attar (Ain Shams University, Egypt)</p> <p>“Empowering Women and Non-Judgmental Linguistic Patterns in Dialectical Behavior Therapy: Case Study of Egyptian Borderline Personality Disorder Female Patients” Walaa Hassan (The British University in Egypt)</p> <p>“Emotive Language in Illness Narratives: Arabic Translation of <i>The Fault in our Stars</i>” Amal Abdelghani (The British University in Egypt)</p>
14:30-15:30 (CLT) (GMT+3) Panel Five	<p style="text-align: center;">Physical Sickness and its Discontents (2)</p> <p>Chair: Ahlam Othman</p> <p>“In the Kingdom of the Sick: Susan Sontag’s “<i>Illness as Metaphor</i>” and the Everyday” Gunnar Lundberg (University of Minnesota, USA)</p> <p>“Making Room for Microbes: Syphilis and Morphine in Henrik Ibsen’s <i>Ghosts</i>” Rania Khalil (The British University in Egypt) (TBC)</p> <p>“Autopathography in Memoirs by Female Writers” Reham Samir (The British University in Egypt)</p>
14:30-15:45 (CLT) (GMT+3)	<p style="text-align: center;">Clinical and Applied Psychology</p> <p>Chair: Reham Attia</p> <p>“The differences between Knowledge and Attitude toward People with Mental Illness among University Students and Academic Staff” Ahmed Abdelaziz (The British University in Egypt)</p> <p>“At the Wormholes of Madness: Neurodivergence and Radical World-Building”</p>

Panel Six	<p>Steven T. Licardi, LCSW (East Side Institute, USA)</p> <p>“The Impact of Perceived Social Support on Postpartum Depression: The Mediating Role of Psychological Capital and Sense of Coherence” Hana Khaled (The British University in Egypt)</p> <p>“The Impact of Sense of Loneliness on Geriatric Depression: The Mediating Role of Sense of Mattering and Psychological Adjustment” Haya Khaled (The British University in Egypt)</p> <p>“Perception, Action, and Executive Function: Understanding the Mechanisms Behind Eating Disorders and OCD” Myar Khaled (The British University in Egypt)</p>
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15:45-16:00 (CLT) (GMT+3)	Break
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Keynote Address 2	
16:00-16:30 (CLT) (GMT+3)	<p style="text-align: center;">Prof. Matthew Reznicek University of Minnesota</p> <p style="text-align: center;">“The Possibilities of the Medical Humanities: Re-Examining Romantic Literature and Body”</p> <p>Chair: Rania Khalil</p>

Parallel Panels: Seven, Eight and Nine	
16:30-17:30 (CLT) (GMT+3)	<p style="text-align: center;">The Periphery and the Potential of Medical Humanities (1)</p> <p>Chair: Rania Salem</p> <p>“Women’s Health in Print: Medicine and Indigenous Knowledge in Colonial Assam” Raktima Bhuyan (Tezpur University, India)</p>

<p>Panel Seven</p>	<p>“Transsexuality and Disease in Rabih Alameddin’s <i>The Wrong End of the Telescope</i>” Noha Hanafy (The British University in Egypt) (TBC)</p> <p>“Symbolic Representations of Stigma of Lepororsy in <i>Yomeeddine</i> (Judgement Day) Film” Nahed Meklash (Matrouh University, Egypt)</p> <p>“The Psychology of the Stressed Psyche in Lee Blessing’s Plays <i>Two Rooms</i> (1990) & <i>A Body of Water</i> (2007): Coping Strategies Investigated” Shaimaa Saeed (The British University in Egypt)</p>
<p>16:30-17:30</p> <p>(CLT) (GMT+3)</p> <p>Panel Eight</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Exploring the Intersection of Stylistics and Discourse Analysis in Medical Humanities</p> <p>Chair: Walaa Hassan</p> <p>“Voices through Masks: A Stylistic Analysis of Selected Covid-19 Pandemic Poems” Neveen Galal-Eldin & Amal M. Zaki Eldin (El-Fayoum University, Egypt)</p> <p>“Trauma Talk – A Corpus-based Cognitive Discourse Analysis of Selected Ted Talks” Rania El-Wakil (MSA University, Egypt)</p> <p>“Unveiling Legitimacy: Analyzing the Power of Persuasion in WHO's Anti-Smoking Publications: A Critical Discourse Analysis “ Hala Shaker (The British University in Egypt)</p>
<p>16:30-17:30</p> <p>(CLT) (GMT+3)</p> <p>Panel Nine</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">The Performative and the Visual in Medical Humanities: Representations</p> <p>Chair: Rania Khalil</p> <p>“Rare: Stories of Dis-Ease” Sonja Kuftinec, James Cloyd, Paul Ranelli, Luverne Seifert (University of Minnesota, USA)</p> <p>“Cultural Visualization of Mental Disorders: Bipolar Disease and Paranoia in Select Texts of Jerry Pinto and Perumal Murugan” Prerona Das (Indian Institute of Technology Design and Manufacturing) & Arif Ahammed (MLR Institute of Technology, India)</p> <p>“Representation Modes of Dementia in Eric Hill’s <i>An Absent Mind</i> and Wendy Mitchell’s <i>Somebody I Used to Know</i>” Faten A. Ramadan (El-Fayoum University, Egypt)</p> <p>“Would the “Real” Mona Lisa smile, please” Sarah Mahmoud Esamel (Suez Canal University, Egypt)</p>

Parallel Panels: Ten and Eleven

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<p>17:30 – 18:30</p> <p>(CLT) (GMT+3)</p> <p>Panel Ten</p>	<p align="center">The Art of Medicine</p> <p>Chair: Matthew Reznicek</p> <p>“My PalliMed Mixtap - An Original Physician Storytelling Project Harnessing the Power of Classic Rock Music and the Accessibility of Blog-based Publishing” Tyler Jorgensen (Dell Medical School, The University of Texas, USA)</p> <p>“Narratives as a Medical Resource: Transforming Patient Interviews into Fictional Stories about Blood Clots” Cintia Vezzani & Alfonso J. Tafur (The University of Tokyo, Japan - NorthShore University, USA)</p> <p>“Lived Experiences of Children with Intellectual Disabilities during the COVID-19 Pandemic” Pariz Pikul Gogoi (Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, India)</p>
<p>17:30 – 18:30</p> <p>(CLT) (GMT+3)</p> <p>Panel Eleven</p>	<p align="center">Engaging Medical Students in Humanities</p> <p>Chair: Ahmed Abdelaziz</p> <p>“Collaborating for Change: Linking Experiential Learning and Historical Evidence in First Year Medical Student Education” Emily Beck, Priya Sury, Lois Hendrickson, Liz Root (University of Minnesota, USA)</p> <p>“Cultivating Empathy: Early Exposure to Person-Centered Art Interactions as Part of Medical Student Training” Jennie Vegt & Pamela Brett-MacLean (University of Alberta, Canada)</p> <p>“The Power of Storytelling: A Novel Curriculum Strategy to Re-engage Physician Interns, Residents, and Fellows in the Art of Medicine” Johnna P. Wellesley (University Texas, USA)</p> <p>“Mental Health Discourses of Medical Students within Kairotic Spaces” Melvin Mathew (Manipal Academy of Higher Education, India)</p>

Parallel Panels: Thirteen and Fourteen

<p>18:30 19:30</p> <p>(CLT) (GMT+3)</p> <p>Panel Twelve</p>	<p>The Poetics and Manifestations of the Pandemic</p> <p>Chair: Noha Hanafy</p> <p>“The Impact of Selected Children Pandemic Poems on English Department Undergraduate Students at the Faculty of Al-Asun (Languages)” Yasser K. R. Aman (Minia University, Egypt)</p> <p>“The Portrayal of Ecocriticism and Trauma in 3 poems written during the Pandemic” Nancy Ihab & Nora Khalil (The British University in Egypt)</p> <p>“Exploring Self and Language in Ali Smith's Companion Piece: A Journey of Discovery during the COVID-19 Lockdown” Rania Salem (The British University in Egypt)</p>
<p>18:30 19:30</p> <p>(CLT) (GMT+3)</p> <p>Panel Thirteen</p>	<p>The Periphery and the Potential of Medical Humanities (2)</p> <p>Chair: Ahlam Othman</p> <p>“Eco-trauma in Palestinian American Fiction: Hala Alyan’s <i>Salt Houses</i> as a Case Study” Pervine Elrefaei (Cairo University, Egypt)</p> <p>“Postcolonial Crossroads of Care in Contemporary French & Francophone Literature: A Research Project and Its Potentials for the Critical Medical Humanities” Julia Proell (University of Innsbruck, Austria)</p> <p>“Mad Women: Representations of Madness in Contemporary Latin American Women’s Literature” Velebita Koričančić (Anahuac University Mexico/ National Autonomous University of Mexico)</p> <p>“Conversion and Recovery Narratives in <i>Hard Times</i> and "Janet's Repentance" Katie Brandt (San Francisco State University, USA)</p>

**Pre-Closing Event
Undergraduate Students Contributions
May 7th, 2024**

**Introduction: Assoc. Prof. Walaa Hassan
Programme Director of the Department of English Language and Literature**

Department of Basic and Applied Psychology Faculty of Arts and Humanities The British University in Egypt	
<p>19:30 - 20:30</p> <p>(CLT) (GMT+3)</p>	<p>Chair: Ansam El-Sheikh</p> <p>“Exploring Creative Thinking in Schizophrenic and Bipolar inpatients: A Comparative Analysis” Ali Mohy (The British University in Egypt)</p> <p>“Avoidant Attachment Style, Gender and Self-esteem as Predictors of Suicidal Ideation” Sama Amr Awad (The British University in Egypt)</p> <p>“Visual Imagery and Logical Analysis: Exploring Phantasia’s Influence on Deductive Reasoning and Gender Dynamics” Yassin El Senoussi & Kenzy Alruwaini (The British University in Egypt)</p> <p>“The effect of social media usage on Bulimia Nervosa on Egyptian adolescents” Bakinam A. Alremaly (The British University in Egypt)</p> <p>“The Relationship between Problematic Mukbang Watching, Unhealthy Eating Patterns, Distorted Body Image, and Eating Disorders among Egyptian Young Adults” Yomna Sabry Balabel (The British University in Egypt)</p>
<p>20:30- 20:45</p> <p>(CLT) (GMT+3)</p>	<p>Closing Remarks Assoc. Professor Rania M Rafik Khalil Symposium Convenor</p>